

PROPERTIES OF THE NUMERICAL FUNCTION F_S

by I. Bălăcenoiu, V. Seleacu, N. Virlan

Department of Mathematics, University of Craiova
Craiova (1100), ROMANIA

In this paper are studied some properties of the numerical function $F_S(x): \mathbb{N} - \{0, 1\} \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ $F_S(x) = \sum_{\substack{0 < p \leq x \\ p \text{ prime}}} S_p(x)$, where $S_p(x) = S(p^x)$ is the Smarandache function defined in [4].

Numerical example: $F_S(5) = S(2^5) + S(3^5) + S(5^5)$; $F_S(6) = S(2^6) + S(3^6) + S(5^6)$.

It is known that: $(p-1)r + 1 \leq S(p^r) \leq pr$ so $(p-1)r < S(p^r) \leq pr$.

Then

$$x(p_1 + p_2 + \dots + p_{\pi(x)} - \pi(x)) < F_S(x) \leq x(p_1 + p_2 + \dots + p_{\pi(x)}) \quad (1)$$

Where $\pi(x)$ is the number of prime numbers smaller or equal with x .

PROPOSITION 1: The sequence $T(x) = 1 - \log F_S(x) + \sum_{i=2}^x \frac{1}{F_S(i)}$ has limit $-\infty$.

Proof. The inequality $F_S(x) > x(p_2 + \dots + p_{\pi(x)} - \pi(x))$ implies $-\log F_S(x) < -\log x(p_1 + p_2 + \dots + p_{\pi(x)} - \pi(x)) < -\log x(\pi(x)p_1 - \pi(x)) = -\log x - \log \pi(x) - \log(p_1 - 1)$.

Then for $x=i$ the inequality (1) become:

$$i(p_1 + \dots + p_{\pi(i)} - \pi(i)) < F_S(i) \leq i(p_1 + \dots + p_{\pi(i)}) \text{ so:}$$

$$\frac{1}{F_S(i)} < \frac{1}{i(p_1 + \dots + p_{\pi(i)} - \pi(i))} < \frac{1}{i(p_1 \pi(i) - \pi(i))} = \frac{1}{i\pi(i)(p_1 - 1)}$$

$$\text{Then } T(x) < 1 - \log(x) - \log \pi(x) - \log(p_1 - 1) + \sum_{i=2}^x \frac{1}{i\pi(i)(p_1 - 1)}$$

$$p_1 = 2 \Rightarrow T(x) = 1 - \log x - \log \pi(x) + \sum_{i=2}^x \frac{1}{i\pi(i)}$$

$$\Rightarrow \lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} T(x) \leq 1 - \lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \log x - \lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \log \pi(x) + \lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{i=2}^x \frac{1}{i\pi(i)} = 1 - \infty - \infty + L = -\infty.$$

PROPOSITION 2. The equation $F_S(x) = F_S(x+1)$ has no solution for $x \in \mathbb{N} - \{0, 1\}$.

Proof. First we consider that $x+1$ is a prime number with $x > 2$. In the particular case $x = 2$ we obtain $F_S(2) = S(2^2) = 4$; $F_S(3) = S(2^3) + S(3^3) = 4 + 9 = 13$. So $F_S(2) < F_S(3)$.

Next we shall write the inequalities:

$$x(p_1 + \dots + p_{\pi(x)} - \pi(x)) < F_S(x) \leq x(p_1 + \dots + p_{\pi(x)}) \quad (2)$$

$$(x+1)(p_1 + \dots + p_{\pi(x)} + p_{\pi(x+1)} - \pi(x+1)) < F_S(x+1) \leq (x+1)(p_1 + \dots + p_{\pi(x)} + p_{\pi(x+1)})$$

Using the reductio ad absurdum method we suppose that the equation $F_S(x) = F_S(x+1)$ has solution. From (2) results the inequalities

$$(x+1)(p_1 + \dots + p_{\pi(x)} + p_{\pi(x+1)} - \pi(x+1)) < F_S(x+1) \leq x(p_1 + \dots + p_{\pi(x)}) \quad (3)$$

From (3) results that:

$$x(p_1 + \dots + p_{\pi(x)}) - (x+1)(p_1 + \dots + p_{\pi(x)} + p_{\pi(x+1)} - \pi(x+1)) > 0$$

$$x(p_1 + \dots + p_{\pi(x)}) - x(p_1 + \dots + p_{\pi(x)}) - xp_{\pi(x+1)} + x\pi(x+1) - p_1 - \dots - p_{\pi(x)} - p_{\pi(x+1)} + \pi(x+1) > 0.$$

But $p_{\pi(x+1)} > \pi(x+1)$ so the difference from above is negative for $x > 0$, and we obtained a contradiction. So $F_S(x) = F_S(x+1)$ has no solution for $x+1$ a prime number.

Next, we demonstrate that the equation $F_S(x) = F_S(x+1)$ has no solution for x and $x+1$ both composite numbers.

Let p be a prime number satisfying conditions $p > \frac{x}{2}$ and $p \leq x-1$. Such p exists according to Bertrand's postulate for every $x \in \mathbf{N} - \{0, 1\}$. Then in the factorial of the number $p(x-1)$, the number p appears at least x times.

So, we have $S(p^x) \leq p(x-1)$.

But $p(x-1) < px + p - x$ (if $p > \frac{x}{2}$) and $px + p - x = (p-1)(x+1) + 1 \leq S(p^{x+1})$.

Therefore $\exists p \leq x-1$ so that $S(p^x) < S(p^{x+1})$.

Then $F_S(x) = S(p_1^x) + \dots + S(p^x) + \dots + S(p_{\pi(x)}^x)$

$$F_S(x+1) = S(p_1^{x+1}) + \dots + S(p^{x+1}) + \dots + S(p_{\pi(x)}^{x+1}) > F_S(x)$$

In conclusion $F_S(x+1) > F_S(x)$ for x and $x+1$ composite numbers. If x is a prime number $\pi(x) = \pi(x+1)$ and the fact that the equation $F_S(x) = F_S(x+1)$ has no solution has the same demonstration as above.

Finally the equation $F_S(x) = F_S(x+1)$ has no solution for any $x \in \mathbf{N} - \{0, 1\}$.

PROPOSITION 3. The function $F_S(x)$ is strictly increasing function on its domain of definition.

The proof. of this property is justified by the proposition 2.

PROPOSITION 4. $F_S(x+y) > F_S(x) + F_S(y) \quad \forall x, y \in \mathbf{N} - \{0, 1\}$.

Proof. Let $x, y \in \mathbf{N} - \{0, 1\}$ and we suppose $x < y$. According to the definition of $F_S(x)$ we have:

$$F(x+y) = S(p_1^{x+y}) + \dots + S(p_{\pi(x)}^{x+y}) + S(p_{\pi(x)+1}^{x+y}) + \dots + S(p_{\pi(y)}^{x+y}) + S(p_{\pi(y)+1}^{x+y}) + \dots + S(p_{\pi(x+y)}^{x+y}) \quad (4)$$

$$F(x) + F(y) = S(p_1^x) + \dots + S(p_{\pi(x)+1}^x) + S(p_1^y) + \dots + S(p_{\pi(x)}^y) + S(p_{\pi(x)+1}^y) + \dots + S(p_{\pi(y)}^x)$$

But from (1) we have the following inequalities:

$$A = (x+y)(p_1 + \dots + p_{\pi(x)} + p_{\pi(x)+1} + \dots + p_{\pi(x+y)} - \pi(x+y)) < F(x+y) \leq \leq (x+y)(p_1 + \dots + p_{\pi(x)} + p_{\pi(x)+1} + \dots + p_{\pi(x+y)}) \quad (5)$$

and

$$x(p_1 + \dots + p_{\pi(x)} - \pi(x)) + y(p_1 + \dots + p_{\pi(x)} + \dots + p_{\pi(x)} + \dots + p_{\pi(y)} - \pi(y)) < F(x) + F(y) \leq \leq x(p_1 + \dots + p_{\pi(x)}) + y(p_1 + \dots + p_{\pi(x)} + p_{\pi(x)+1} + \dots + p_{\pi(y)}) = B \quad (6)$$

We proof that $B < A$.

$$\begin{aligned} B < A &\Leftrightarrow x(p_1 + \dots + p_{\pi(x)}) + y(p_1 + \dots + p_{\pi(x)} + y(p_{\pi(x)+1} + \dots + p_{\pi(y)})) < \\ &x(p_1 + \dots + p_{\pi(x)}) + y(p_1 + \dots + p_{\pi(x)}) + x(p_{\pi(x)+1} + \dots + p_{\pi(x+y)}) - x\pi(x+y) + \\ &+ y(p_{\pi(x)+1} + \dots + p_{\pi(y)}) + y(p_{\pi(y)+1} + \dots + p_{\pi(x+y)}) - y\pi(x+y) \Leftrightarrow \\ &x(p_{\pi(x)+1} + \dots + p_{\pi(x+y)} - \pi(x+y)) + y(p_{\pi(y)+1} + \dots + p_{\pi(x+y)} - \pi(x+y)) > 0 \end{aligned}$$

But $p_{\pi(x+y)} \geq \pi(x+y)$ so that the inequality from above is true.

CONSEQUENCE: $F_S(xy) > F_S(x) + F_S(y) \quad \forall x, y \in \mathbb{N} - \{0, 1\}$

Because x and $y \in \mathbb{N} - \{0, 1\}$ and $xy > x + y$ than $F_S(xy) > F_S(x+y) > F_S(x) + F_S(y)$

PROPOSITION 5. We try to find $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{F_S(n)}{n^\alpha}$

We have $F_S(n) = \sum_{\substack{0 < p_i \leq n \\ p_i = \text{prime}}} S(p_i^n)$ and:

$$\frac{p_1 + p_2 + \dots + p_{\pi(n)} - \pi(n)}{n^{\alpha-1}} < \frac{F_S(n)}{n^\alpha} \leq \frac{p_1 + p_2 + \dots + p_{\pi(n)}}{n^{\alpha-1}}$$

If $\alpha < 1$ than

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} n^{1-\alpha}(p_1 + \dots + p_{\pi(n)} - \pi(n)) = \infty \cdot \infty = +\infty \Rightarrow \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{F_S(n)}{n^{\alpha-1}} = +\infty.$$

If $\alpha = 1$ than

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} n^{1-\alpha}(p_1 + \dots + p_{\pi(n)} - \pi(n)) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} (p_1 + \dots + p_{\pi(n)} - \pi(n)) = +\infty \Rightarrow \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{F_S(n)}{n^{\alpha-1}} = +\infty$$

We consider now $\alpha > 1$.

We try to find $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{\pi(n)} p_i - \pi(n)}{n^{\alpha-1}}$ and $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{\pi(n)} p_i}{n^{\alpha-1}}$ applying Stolz - Cesaro:

Let $a_n = \sum_{i=1}^{\pi(n)} p_i - \pi(n)$ and $b_n = n^{\alpha-1}$.

$$\text{Than : } \frac{a_{n+1} - a_n}{b_{n+1} - b_n} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{\pi(n+1)} p_i - \pi(n+1) - \sum_{i=1}^{\pi(n)} p_i + \pi(n)}{(n+1)^{\alpha-1} - n^{\alpha-1}} = \begin{cases} \frac{n}{(n+1)^{\alpha-1} - n^{\alpha-1}} \\ \text{if } (n+1) \text{ is a prime} \\ 0, \text{ otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Let $c_n = \sum_{i=1}^{\pi(n)} p_i$ and $d_n = n^{\alpha-1}$.

$$\text{Than } \frac{c_{n+1} - c_n}{d_{n+1} - d_n} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{\pi(n+1)} p_i - \sum_{i=1}^{\pi(n)} p_i}{(n+1)^{\alpha-1} - n^{\alpha-1}} = \frac{p_{\pi(n+1)}}{(n+1)^{\alpha-1} - n^{\alpha-1}} = \begin{cases} \frac{n+1}{(n+1)^{\alpha-1} - n^{\alpha-1}} \text{ if} \\ (n+1) \text{ is a prime} \\ 0, \text{ otherwise} \end{cases}$$

First we consider the limit of the function.

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \frac{x}{(x+1)^{\alpha-1} - x^{\alpha-1}} = \lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{(\alpha-1)[(x+1)^{\alpha-2} - x^{\alpha-2}]} = 0 \text{ for } \alpha-2 > 1$$

We used the l'Hospital theorem:

In the same way we have

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \frac{x+1}{(x+1)^{\alpha-1} - x^{\alpha-1}} = 0 \text{ for } \alpha > 3.$$

So, for $\alpha > 3$ we have:

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \frac{p_1 + p_2 + \dots + p_{\pi(n)} - \pi(n)}{n^{\alpha-1}} = 0 \text{ and}$$

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \frac{p_1 + p_2 + \dots + p_{\pi(n)}}{n^{\alpha-1}} = 0. \quad \text{So } \lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \frac{F(n)}{n^\alpha} = 0.$$

$$\text{Finally } \lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \frac{F(n)}{n^\alpha} = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{for } \alpha > 3 \\ +\infty & \text{for } \alpha \leq 1 \end{cases}$$

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- [1] M. Andrei, C. Dumitrescu, V. Seleacu, L. Tuțescu, Șt. Zanfir *Some remarks on the Smarandache Function*, Smarandache Function Journal, Vol. 4, No.1 (1994) 1-5;
- [2] P. Gronas *A note on $S(p^r)$* , Smarandache Function Journal, V. 2-3, No.1 (1993) 33;
- [3] M. Andrei, I. Bălăcenoiu, C. Dumitrescu, E. Rădescu, N. Rădescu, V. Seleacu *A linear combination with Smarandache Function to obtain the Identity*, Proceedings of 26th Annual Iranian Mathematic Conference Shahid Baharar University of Kerman , Kerman - Iran March 28 - 31 1995
- [4] F. Smarandache *A Function in the Number Theory*, An. Univ. Timișoara, Ser. St. Mat. Vol. XVIII, fasc. 1(1980) 9, 79-88.